

Welcome to the EXA4MIND Newsletter

Who are we? We are a Horizon Europe project that aims to build an extreme data platform that brings together large scale data storage systems and powerful computing infrastructures by implementing novel automated data management and effective data staging.

Editorial

**Stephan Hachinger, Science and Co-design Coordinator of
EXA4MIND**

A banner with a purple and blue background featuring a network of white lines and dots. On the left is a circular portrait of Stephan Hachinger. The main text is in white, and there are logos for EXA4MIND and the European Union at the bottom left.

**Welcome to the
6th EXA4MIND
Newsletter!**

By Stephan Hachinger,
Science and Co-design Coordinator of EXA4MIND

EXA4MIND

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Dear Reader!

We welcome you to the 6th EXA4MIND Newsletter, the first after our interim review. In 22 months of this thriving project, we have developed extreme data analytics workflows involving supercomputing power, optimised data backends in an Extreme Data Database (EDD), and an Advanced Query and Indexing

System (AQIS).

With maturing architecture and platform components, the Application Cases have shown us what is possible with technology for massive data analytics. For example, an Automated Data Mining System for Systematic Improvement in Molecular Simulations (ADMS4SIMS) enables collaborative analysis for unprecedented improvements in molecular dynamics. Supercomputing power and enhanced data backends enable methods for image segmentation and annotation, making automated driving assistance systems more efficient, and reliability is improved by advanced failure detection. Soil moisture prediction for smart farming can be realised by AI, inferring the moisture from recent weather data and satellite imagery. Last but not least, flexible tools have been developed for the analysis of public health data, helping to construct sustainable healthcare systems.

All these Application Cases were presented at the review, together with the platform concept and the realisation of the first version of flexibly-deployable modules of the EXA4MIND platform, which will be made available open-source and can be instantiated by anyone on different target systems to build big and extreme data analytics workflows. The technology behind these modules, from data backends over workflow control, to indexing, streaming and caching tools, are the essence of what our Application Cases require in every day practice. We are proud that our work, up to now, satisfied the reviewers who encouraged us to generalise our techniques further during the second half of the project - a path which we will pursue and had already foreseen in our project planning.

In this Newsletter we have selected a few other highlights from our current activities to share with you. We hope that reading about them below will spark some inspiration for you! Enjoy!

Participation in international events

The DataNexus cluster conquers EBDVF 2024

The [European Big Data Value Forum \(EBDVF\) 2024](#) took place from 2 to 4 October in Budapest, Hungary. The three-day conference, organised by the [Big Data Value Association](#), in collaboration with [AI&AUT EXPO](#), [Eötvös Loránd University \(ELTE\)](#), [Ideal-ist](#), [Neumann Technology Platform](#) and the [Institute for Computer Science and Control \(SZTAKI\)](#), brought together industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policy-makers from all over Europe and other regions of the world to advance policy actions and industrial and research activities in the areas of Data and AI. Following the success of the 2023 edition, **EXA4MIND** returned to EBDVF, this time as part of the **DataNexus cluster**.

Under the theme "Europe for global leadership in AI & Data" the EBDVF 2024 featured 43 workshops, sessions and plenaries bringing together 180 speakers. [The DataNexus cluster](#) contributed to these impressive numbers with a [90 minutes session](#) entitled "Innovative Approaches to Extreme Data Challenges".

[Discover more](#)

ELIXIR CZ Annual Conference 2024: Data management

DM in EU context
Tools, Workflows
Community, Best Practice
NRP, EOSC, OS II

9 - 11 October, 2024, Prague
<https://www.elixir-czech.cz>

EXA4MIND
PRESENTED AT THE
ELIXIR CZ ANNUAL
CONFERENCE 2024

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EXA4MIND presented at the ELIXIR CZ Annual Conference 2024

The ninth [ELIXIR CZ annual conference](#), which focused on data management topics, took place from 9 to 11 October 2024. **Martin Golasowski** from [IT4Innovations](#) presented [iRODS](#) as a solution for distributed data management in the Tools and Workflows session. This tool is supported as one of the methods for data movement in the EXA4MIND project. **Jan Martinovič**, the **coordinator of the EXA4MIND** project also took part in the ELIXIR CZ Annual Conference 2024.

Discover more

EXA4MIND attends SC24

The international conference for high-performance computing, networking, storage, and analysis ([SC24](#)) took place from 17 to 22 November at the Georgia World Congress Center in Atlanta, US. One of the exhibitors was [IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center](#). **EXA4MIND** was visible at the conference since the team led by Jan Martinovič **promoted its activities and application cases** at booth no. 4233.

Discover more

Campaign: Faces of EXA4MIND

With the **series "Faces of EXA4MIND"** we want to introduce the people who work every day to achieve our ambitious goal: Building a platform for Extreme Data that enables advanced data analytics on supercomputers and automated data management with support for integration by design with EOSC and European data spaces.

**FACES OF
EXA4MIND**

**MEET THE PEOPLE BEHIND
THE EXA4MIND PROJECT**

WP1 (ARCHITECTURE CO-
DESIGN) LEADER

MARTIN GOLASOWSKI

Martin Golasowski (IT4Innovations)

We present **Martin Golasowski** from [IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center](#) and the WP1 (Architecture Co-design) leader of EXA4MIND. When asked what makes this project special, he is clear about it: *"The most positive impact of the project is bringing together the world of databases and their instances to the world of Supercomputing with the batch processing and job scheduling. And solving many interesting issues, which appeared along the way, which are mainly related to the data transfers and the differences between the different infrastructures, which those two worlds are using".*

[Watch his interview](#)

The DataNexus Cluster

Extreme Data Challenges: Managing Large, Fast-Moving, and Diverse Datasets Efficiently and Effectively.

Discover the DataNexus cluster: Advanced Solutions for Big Data & Artificial Intelligence Challenges

Dive into the world of advanced data management and discover how seven pioneering EU-funded projects – [Graph-Massivizer](#), [EXTRACT EU](#), [NearData](#), [EMERALDS](#), [SYCLOPS](#), [EFRA](#) and [EXA4MIND](#) – join forces in the [DataNexus cluster](#). Together, we are pushing the boundaries of big data, AI, IoT and advanced computing to help navigate the complexities of today's data-driven landscape.

Watch our latest video to find out what the DataNexus cluster is capable of!

Meet the projects behind the DataNexus cluster

For the first time, the projects of the [DataNexus cluster](#) met at the **European Big Data Value Forum** in Budapest ([EBDVF 2024](#)). We took the opportunity to get to know the faces behind each of them.

Press play and discover the essence of each project and what they expect from the cluster!

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